

3-Hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of tungsten(VI)

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Abstract : A simple, rapid, sensitive and highly selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of tungsten in trace amounts is developed using 3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HMPB) as a reagent for the complexation of metal ion and extracting the 1 : 4 (metal : ligand) complex into dichloromethane from 0.2 M HClO₄ solution. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0–3.8 μg W^{VI} ml⁻¹, with a molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of 3.78 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0049 μg W cm⁻², respectively at 407 nm. The method is free from the interference of a large number (38) of analytically important elements such as alkaline earth metal ions, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Mo, Zr, Nb, U, Re, Se, Ce, Sn, As and platinum metals. The proposed system handles satisfactorily the analysis of several samples of varying complexity.

Keywords : Tungsten(vi), spectrophotometric determination.

The often used thiocyanate, vanadophosphoric acid and dithiol methods¹ for the trace determination of tungsten spectrophotometrically suffer from a large number of interferences, lack sensitivity and are time consuming. Recently reported methods using several other organic reagents²⁻⁵ for this purpose also suffer from one or the other of these drawbacks. Accordingly, a study of the complex reaction of 3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HMPB) with tungsten(vi) has been presented below with a view to develop a better extractive spectrophotometric method for trace determination of the element.

Results and discussion

Effect of nature of acids on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex : A light yellow complex of tungsten(vi) was formed with HMPB in acidic medium which was quantitatively extractable into dichloromethane. The absorbance of the complex in the solvent was influenced by the nature and concentration of the acids. From 0.2 M acidity in each case, the absorbance was found to decrease in the order : HClO₄ > HCl > H₂SO₄ > CH₃COOH > H₃PO₄. The complex gave very low absorbance (0.010) in the alkaline medium as observed with NaOH (0.2 M). Therefore, HClO₄ medium was preferred for further studies.

Effect of various organic solvents on the absorbance of W^{VI} complex : Tungsten(vi)-HMPB complex was extracted

into a large number of water immiscible organic solvents. The absorbance in the organic extract decreased in the order : dichloromethane > chloroform > toluene > benzene = 1,2-dichloroethane > isobutylmethylketone > ethyl acetate > carbon tetrachloride > amyl acetate > amyl alcohol > cyclohexane. As dichloromethane gave maximum absorbance with a rapid and clear phase separation, it was chosen as the most suitable extractant. A single equilibration of the aqueous phase with equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane under optimum conditions gave quantitative (100%) recovery of W^{VI}-HMPB complex. The complete absence of tungsten in the raffinate was tested by the more sensitive 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran method³.

λ_{max} and stability of the complex : The absorption spectrum of the complex indicated that the maximum lied at 403–411 nm in the visible region, where the reagent blank had minimal absorbance. The coloured complex of tungsten(vi) formed with HMPB under optimum conditions, was stable for more than 20 h in dichloromethane at 407 nm.

Effect of concentration of HClO₄, HMPB and equilibration time on the absorbance of the complex : The optimum values of other parameters found for achieving maximum and constant absorbance were : 0.14–0.26 M HClO₄, 0.5–1.3 ml of 0.1% HMPB in acetone and 7–240 s equilibration

Note

Table 1. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of the W-complex

HClO ₄ (M) ^a	0.04	0.08	0.12	0.14–0.26	0.28	0.30
Absorbance	0.310	0.360	0.390	0.410	0.395	0.380
0.1% HMPB (ml) ^b	0.2	0.4	0.5–1.3	1.4	1.5	2.0
Absorbance	0.290	0.370	0.410	0.390	0.370	0.300
Equilibration time (s) ^c	0	5	7–240			
Absorbance	0.050	0.390	0.410			

^aW^{VI} = 20 µg, HClO₄ = variable, 0.1% HMPB = 0.5 ml, equilibration time = 30 s, solvent = dichloromethane, aqueous volume = solvent volume = 10 ml, number of extractions = 1; ^bHClO₄ = 0.2 M, other conditions being the same as in (a) except for the variation in HMPB concentration, also ^b3-hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HMPB); ^c0.1% HMPB in acetone = 0.7 ml, other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

Table 2. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous conditions	Solvent (λ _{max} , nm)	Sandell's sensitivity (µg cm ⁻²) (Molar absorptivity dm ³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Interfering metal ions
1.	W ^{VI} , conc. HCl, SnCl ₂ , 0.5% dithiol (in amyl acetate), heat to 80°, wash the extract with conc. HCl, takes longer time ^a	Amyl acetate (640)	0.0096 (1.92 × 10 ⁴)	Mo ^{VI} separated by extraction as dithiolate from 1.9 M HCl before determination of W ^{VI}
2.	W ^{VI} , 20% KSCN, 40% SnCl ₂ , 8–9 M HCl, colour development time 15 min ^a	Isoamyl alcohol (403)	0.012 (1.56 × 10 ⁴)	Hg ^{II} , Au ^{III} , Pt ^{IV} , Cr ^{VI} , Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II} , As ^V , V ^V
3.	W ^{VI} , stilbazogal I, acetate-acetic acid buffer, pH 4.9, colour development time 5–15 min ^a	– (520)	0.0049 (3.76 × 10 ⁴)	Al ^{III} , Cr ^{III,VI} , Cu ^{II} , Mo ^{VI} , Ti ^{IV} , Th ^{IV} , V ^V , Zr ^{IV}
4.	W ^{VI} , 0.02% 3,5-dinitrocatechol in ethanol, 2.5 M HCl, pH 1, colour development time 20 min ^a	– (400)	–	Nb ^V , Ta ^V , Ti ^{IV} , V ^V , Sn ^{II} , Ge ^{III}
5.	W ^{VI} , 1 M H ₃ PO ₄ (vanadophosphoric acid) ^a	– (360–460)	0.33 (6.21 × 10 ²)	Bi ^{III} , Pb ^{II} , Th ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Fe ^{III} , Cr ^{VI} , Mn ^{VII}
6.	W ^{VI} , 10 M HCl, 25% KSCN, 30% SnCl ₂ , 0.5% quinaldic acid, heat to 80°, colour development time 10 min ^b	Isoamyl acetate (405)	0.012 (1.51 × 10 ⁴)	Mo ^{VI} , Pd ^{II} , Ti ^{IV} , Re ^{VII} , V ^V , Pt ^{IV}
7.	W ^{VI} , 0.2 M HCl, 0.6–2.1 ml of 0.1% 3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran in ethanol, takes longer time ^c	Dichloromethane (415)	0.0029 (6.45 × 10 ⁴)	Mo ^{VI} separated by extraction as thiocyanate complex in presence of NaF before determination of W ^{VI}
8.	W ^{VI} , pH 0.8–2.4, 2,4-dihydroxybenzenethiol ^d	Isoamyl alcohol (490)	0.046 (0.4 × 10 ⁴)	Not known
9.	Proposed method	Dichloromethane (407)	0.0049 (3.78 × 10 ⁴)	38 metal ions do not interfere

^aRef 1. ^bRef. 2. ^cRef. 3. ^dRef. 4.

time for ≤ 38 µg W^{VI} per 10 ml aqueous volume (Table 1). The order of addition of acid and the reagent should be the same as per the proposed procedure, otherwise low absorbance was observed.

Beer's law range, molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and composition of the complex : Beer's law was valid in the tungsten concentration range of 0–3.8 µg ml⁻¹. However, the optimum range of determination of tungsten as evaluated from Ringbom plot⁶ was found to be 0.79–3.63 µg ml⁻¹. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 407 nm were 3.78 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0049 µg W cm⁻², respectively. The metal to ligand stoichiometry has been established by Job's method of continuous variations⁷ as modified by Vosburgh and

Cooper⁸ to be 1 : 4 which was further confirmed by the mole-ratio method⁹.

Effect of diverse ions : Under the optimum conditions of the procedure in 10 ml aqueous volume (mg amounts in parentheses), bromide, nitrate, sulfate, thiourea and carbonate (100 each); EDTA 'disodium salt' and dithionite (80 each); chloride, iodide and sulfosalicylic acid (70 each); phosphate, thiocyanate, hydrazine sulfate and ascorbic acid (50 each); acetate (20); citrate and tartrate (5 each); fluoride (0.5) and glycerol (0.1 ml) were without effect. However, oxalate and H₂O₂ interfered seriously. Among the cations, Co^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II}, Zn^{II}, Mn^{II} and As^V (10 each); Ni^{II}, Mg^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} (9 each); Bi^{III} (8); Al^{III} (7); Cd^{II} (5); Be^{II} and Se^{IV} (4 each); U^{VI} (3); Cr^{III} and Os^{VIII} (2 each); Sb^{III},

Ce^{IV} and Cr^{VI} (1 each); Th^{IV} and Cu^{II} (0.5 each); Fe^{III} (0.4); V^V and Pt^{IV} (0.3 each); Ta^V, Nb^V and Ir^{III} (0.1 each); Au^{III} and Re^{VII} (0.09 each); Ti^{IV} and Ru^{III} (0.05 each) and Pd^{II} (0.04) caused $\leq 1\%$ error in absorbance. Zr^{IV}, Mo^{VI} and Sn^{II} did not interfere in presence of respective masking agents as described under the procedure.

Applications : The wide applicability of the method was tested by the analysis of several synthetic (some of them analogous to minargent, platinumoid, W-alloy, heat resistant steel, high speed steel and stellite No. 2) and reverberatory flue dust samples with satisfactory results. The proposed spectrophotometric method is highly selective, fast, sensitive and is free from the interference of a large number of analytically important ions including platinum metals. The results obtained were highly reproducible with a standard deviation of ± 0.0015 absorbance units. The proposed method had certainly an advantage over the existing methods (Table 2) as regards sensitivity, selectivity and rapidity.

Experimental

A standard stock solution (100 ml) of tungsten(vi) containing 1 mg ml^{-1} of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount (0.179 g) of sodium tungstate (L.R., C.D.H.) in deionized water and standardized by the oxine method¹. Lower concentrations at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level were prepared by suitable dilution therefrom. Solutions of other ions were prepared at mg ml^{-1} level by dissolving their sodium or potassium salts in deionized water or dilute acids. They were suitably diluted to obtain lower concentrations of the metal ions at $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ level. Perchloric acid (Qualigens excelaR[®]) 2 M was prepared by diluting 70% (11.6 M) acid with deionized water. 3-Hydroxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HMPB), m.p. 234 °C was synthesized by the literature method¹⁰ and dissolved in acetone to get 0.1% (w/v) solution. Dichloromethane (RANKEM) was used as such. A UV-Vis (Shimadzu 140-02) spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched glass cells was used for routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies.

Synthetic samples (some of them analogous to technical samples such as minargent, platinumoid, W-alloy, heat resistant steel, high speed steel and stellite No. 2) were prepared by mixing the solutions of various metal ions in suitable proportions. Reverberatory flue dust sample¹¹ (0.1 g) from copper manufacture containing no tungsten was mixed with a solution of known tungsten content (1 mg) and dried in an oven at 110–120 °C. After fusion of the dried dust sample with sodium peroxide (0.8 g), the leach was treated with 0.5 g sodium potassium tartrate, neutral-

ized with concentrated HClO₄ and adjusted to 2 M acidity in 100 ml final volume. Aliquots (1 and 1.5 ml) were taken for the determination of tungsten by the proposed method. All these experiments show excellent results.

Procedure : To the sample solution containing $\leq 38 \mu\text{g}$ tungsten(vi) and other ions taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel were added 2 M perchloric acid (1 ml), 0.1% (w/v) HMPB (0.7 ml) and sufficient deionized water to make up the volume to 10 ml. It was then equilibrated once with an equal volume (10 ml) of dichloromethane for 30 s. The layers were allowed to separate and the light yellow organic phase was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41 (pretreated with dichloromethane) to remove water droplets, if any. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 407 nm against a similarly treated reagent blank and the amount of tungsten was determined from the standard curve prepared in an analogous manner.

For 0.4 mg Zr^{IV} was added 50 mg sodium phosphate. For 0.004 mg Mo^{VI} was added 5 mg sodium potassium tartrate and for 0.1 mg Sn^{II} was added 80 mg EDTA 'disodium salt', as masking agents, prior to the addition of HMPB in 10 ml aqueous volume.

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